

Development of an Artificial Intelligence (AI) based Image Processing System for Industrial Sorting of Big Onion

H.A.S.V. Attanayake¹, K.S.P. Amaratunga¹, K.P. Chathumal¹, C. Wangmo²

ABSTRACT

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is a culinary staple worldwide with retail markets use relying on manual sorting processes to deliver high quality onions to customers. This study explores the use of machine learning techniques in artificial intelligence (AI) for image processing to enhance this sorting process. Specifically, the SSD MobileNetV2 (MobileNet Single Shot Detector) model, utilizing Open CV and TensorFlow Python modules, was employed to classify onions into pre-determined categories quality, rotten, sprouted and double bulbs. Image acquisition was carried out using a Pi Camera module and a Raspberry Pi Single Board Computer, with the acquired images used for training, validating and testing the model. The developed TensorFlow Lite model was then evaluated in real-time, achieving an overall mAP of 77.94%, F1 Score of 0.82, accuracy of 91.62%, precision of 83.90% and recall value of 82.92% under controlled lighting conditions. This model demonstrates the potential for industrial onion sorting with a conveyor belt feeding system.

Keywords: Big onion; Image Processing; Raspberry Pi; SSD Mobile Net V2; TensorFlow.

1. INTRODUCTION

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is a key culinary ingredient in Sri Lanka and worldwide. The underground bulb of this monocot plant, in the Alliaceae is family of the Liliopsida class, is primarily consumed. Consumers select high-quality onions by evaluating external characteristics such as color, shape, size, odor, and sprouted. However, in supermarket chains in Sri Lanka, where large quantities of onion and other agricultural produce are handled, manual sorting is done before reaching customers. Typically, these supermarket chains have regional collection centers where onions are brought in bulk and sorted manually.

Data from the Cargill Fruit and Vegetable Collection Center in Wattala, Sri Lanka, shows that the rate of manual onion sorting is 156 kg per man-hour. In Sri Lanka, only 23.71% of onions are domestically produced (Rambukwella *et al.*, 2022) with the majority being imported. The countries onion demand is primarily met through imports, mainly from India, Holland, and occasionally Pakistan, based on bilateral agreements between the countries. Among the imported varieties, Indian onions are particularly popular for their well-cured nature, preferred shape, distinctive light magenta color, and pungency. The 'Pusa Red' variety imported from India is the most favored among Sri Lankans due to its pungency, color, and shape.

¹Department of Agricultural Engineering, University of Peradeniya, Peradeniya, Sri Lanka.

²Agriculture Machinery Technology Centre, Department of Agriculture, Paro, Bhutan.

*Corresponding author – email:sunimaliattanayake@gmail.com

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In supermarket chains, big onions are sorted into different quality parameters before reaching customers to provide premium quality. According to Cargill Food City Supermarket Chain's quality parameters, well-cured onions weighing between 40g and 200g with single undamaged outer scales are accepted for premium quality. Onions that are rotten, sprouted, double bulbs, have two scales, damaged outer scales or unsealed necks are rejected.

Due to labour – intensive and time – consuming of these sorting procedures, image processing techniques related to Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence can be used to enhance sorting efficiency. Image processing techniques have been used for many agricultural processes for identification purposes (Sharma, 2021) and have contributed to the sustainability of world agriculture (Sachithra and Subhashini, 2023). In the market, there are many onion grading machines used for grading the onions into different size categories. However, the availability of industrially suitable machinery for sorting onions using image processing techniques is very less. This is due to the availability of many varieties of onions in the world market and the less availability of rich image datasets containing different varieties of onions and their defects. In developing countries like Sri Lanka, utilizing high-tech machines can be costly, making it more economical to hire people initially rather than investing in sophisticated equipment. Leveraging existing technologies, like Raspberry Pi single board computers and Pi Camera modules, can provide cost – effective solutions for sorting onions without straining finances.

Incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) can significantly benefit the the agricultural sector and help feed the growing world population. Technical advancements, like big data analytics, robotics, the internet of things, the low-cost sensors and cameras, drone technology, and widespread internet connectivity in geographically separated

fields, enable the application of AI in agriculture (Eli-chukwu, 2019). AI is used in various areas of agriculture, including general crop management (Sharma, 2021), pest and disease management, disease management, agricultural product monitoring and storage control, and soil and irrigation management (Bannerjee *et al.*, 2018).

The edible part of a big onion consists of swollen leaves arranged concentrically around a stem. Due to their high moisture content, onion bulbs prone to microbial infections and mechanical damage (Saibu *et al.* 2019). Countries like China, India, the United States, Egypt, Turkey, Pakistan, Sudan, Bangladesh, and Iran are major producers of onions (Paymode *et al.*, 2021). Sri Lanka producing less than its domestic requirement, needs to improve curing and storage conditions for big onions. Curing is a process that removes excess moisture from the neck. Curing is a special process as moisture is only removed from the outer layer of the onion bulb, not from the entire bulb. This can be done by windrowing the onions in the fields or by providing artificial or forced air (Gorrepati *et al.*, 2017) and thereby physiological weight loss, rotting of the bulbs, sprouting of the bulbs, and the overall postharvest losses are reduced (Nega, *et al.*, 2015). Sorting and grading are done to improve the market value of the produce (Gayathri, 2023). So the developed automatic sorting devices should have the ability to detect materials on a sorting surface (usually a sorting bed or a conveyor) and automatic removal of the impurities in bulks (Dorokhov *et al.* 2021). Unless manual labor is used, these operations consume huge amounts of energy and as the harvested produce is handled many times during these processes, it increases wastage resulting poor market value of the produces. Most of the grading machines are mechanical graders, grading depending on the size, shape, color, and weight of the onions (Gayathri, 2023). The most common manual grading machines are roller and sieve machines. But they are not capable of sorting

onions according to the quality parameters. Therefore, machine learning has been used in sorting onions using image processing techniques with Raspberry Pi Single computers (Dorokhov *et al.* 2021). Detection of infected and non-infected onions based on their external characteristics has been done using various methods. A machine imaging system is an inexpensive instrument that provides accurate onion bulb assessment, fast processing, and dependable operation (Waghmare *et al.*, 2024). A computerized method for identifying images that focuses on the fruit's imperfections both internally and externally has been produced (Njoroge *et al.*, 2002). Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) based onion sorting systems have been developed to identify good quality and damaged onions using the Fruit 360 database Waghmare *et al.*, 2024). This is an open-source database available with a collection of 100×100 fruit images of 131 varieties of fruits in the world (Fruits – 360).

TensorFlow is widely recognized as a versatile machine learning framework that is particularly effective for image processing tasks, such as image classification and recognition, through the use of deep neural networks (DNNs) and convolutional neural networks (CNNs) (Yadav *et al.*, 2022). These models are integral to image classification, a subset of image processing, which involves assigning categories to images based on their content (Devi *et al.*, 2021). This is used in hierarchical image classification for waste object detection and edge-aware image filtering to preserve significant edges without post-processing steps (Kim *et al.*, 2020). Its use in various studies underscores its capability to facilitate complex image classification and processing procedures, contributing to narrowing the gap between computer and human vision (Yadav *et al.*, 2021), as well as enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of image analysis across different applications (Kim *et al.*, 2020). These networks are characterized by their use of convolution operations, which allow them to capture local and global features in data, and their ability to form hierarchical representations.

CNNs have been successfully applied in areas such as psychiatry, neurology, computer vision, and pattern recognition, demonstrating their versatility and effectiveness (Zhou, 2018). Interestingly, despite their widespread use and success, the theoretical foundations of CNNs, such as their universality of approximation, are not fully understood (Pinaya *et al.*, 2020). Recent studies have started to address these gaps, showing that CNNs can approximate any continuous function given sufficient depth (Han *et al.* 2023). Additionally, CNNs have been adapted to preserve specific invariances, such as gauge equivariance in lattice gauge theories, which traditional CNNs cannot capture (Favoni *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, CNNs are a powerful tool in deep learning with a wide range of applications and are distinguished by their structured architecture, which enables them to efficiently process and learn from high-dimensional data. While there is ongoing research to fully understand their theoretical properties, the practical successes of CNNs are undeniable, and they continue to be a focal point of innovation in machine learning (Xu *et al.*, 2020).

Supervised learning in machine learning is a paradigm where models are trained using labelled data, which means that the input data is paired with the correct output (Saravanan & Renuka, 2018). In the context of object detection, supervised learning algorithms require a dataset with annotated images where the locations and categories of objects are specified (Xu *et al.*, 2020). This approach is widely used due to its effectiveness in learning from the provided annotations to detect and classify objects in new images. However, the production of labelled datasets for object detection is labor-intensive and costly, which limits the scalability of supervised learning methods (Zhang *et al.*, 2020).

SSD MobileNet V2 is a Convolutional Neural Network architecture that aims to perform well on mobile devices. It is based on an inverted residual structure where the residual connections are

between the bottleneck layers. The Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD) framework, when combined with MobileNet V2, is a powerful architecture for object detection tasks, especially when transfer learning is applied. The integration of SSD with MobileNet V2 is optimized for real-time processing, offering a balance between speed and accuracy (Cai *et al.*, 2020). Thus SSD MobileNet V2 is a viable option for transfer learning applications, providing a good trade-off between detection speed and accuracy. However, its performance on small target detection could be a potential area for further optimization (Zhang *et al.*, 2020).

Therefore, this research aims to develop and evaluate an AI based image processing system to accurately sort onions based on predefined quality parameters with enhanced sorting efficiency, reduced labour dependency while ensuring high classification accuracy.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Onion Classification Workflow Overview

Onion sorting was a high-labor-cost process, and to address this challenge, an Artificial Intelligence-based image processing system was developed for use in an industrial setting. The first step was to establish sorting criteria, which included good quality onions, double bulbs, sprouted onions, and rotten onions. Images of onion from each category were then obtained, annotated and used to train the model. The

TensorFlow Lite model in a Google Colab Notebook using the annotated images. The model was then deployed and run on a Windows 10 (PC) through PyCharm IDE (Integrated Development Environment). Validation of the model was conducted using images and also by running the model with onion samples in real time.

2.2 Image Acquisition and Annotation Process

Data acquisition was a crucial part of the project as the rest of the project relied on the images of onions captured for the four different classes of onions. As the first step, illumination of the onions was needed. It was done by building a light box. The box was illuminated by using a WS2811 addressable RGB LED strip connected to an Arduino Uno Board to provide lighting of the colour combination 200, 255, 200 RGB. The LED strip was attached to a reflector (Fig. 1) and a diffuser (Fig. 2). A Pi Camera module v 1.3 and a Raspberry Pi 3 was used for capturing the images.

The interior of the light box was painted white to ensure uniform illumination. Images of the four classes of onions were captured using the Pi Camera module and saved in the .jpg (Joint Photographic Experts Group) format. The images were then annotated using the LabelImg Tool to convert them into .xml (Extensible Markup Language) format. The Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the LabelImg Tool is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 1. WS2811 LED strip attached to the reflector

Fig. 2. Pi Camera module attached to the diffuser

Fig. 1. Graphical user interface (GUI) of the Labelling tool

A total of 440 images were obtained and they were classified for model training, validation and testing in the following manner.

Table 1. Image allocation for model training, validating and testing

Class	Train	Validation	Test
Good	88	11	11
Double	88	11	11
Rotten	88	11	11
Sprouted	88	11	11
Total	352	44	44

2.3. Model Training Using TensorFlow and OpenCV on Google Colab

After annotating the images, the TensorFlow model was trained using the Google Colab Notebook (by Google LLC.). The GPU (Graphical Processing Units) memory of Google Colab Notebook, along with the OpenCV (a community developed and managed library with major contributions from Intel) and TensorFlow (owned by Google LLC). Python modules, were used to develop the TensorFlow object detection model. The number of training steps and batch size were set to 20,000 and 16, respectively. Once the TensorFlow model was created, it was tested using images of onions that were not used during the training the process.

Following are the specifications used in training the model.

Images per class: 110

Total images : 440

Split : 80% training, 10% validation, 10% testing (manually split with script)

Model : SSD MobileNetV2 FPN-Lite 320x320 (COCO trained, TensorFlow 2.8)

Layer freezing : Early layers were frozen, later layers fine-tuned

Batch size : 16

Training steps : 20,000

While there are other models available, such as the YOLOv4 model for real-time image classification, SSD MobileNetV2 was chosen for its low latency and real-time performance, which are crucial for onion sorting on Raspberry Pi 3B. Although YOLOv4 provided slightly higher accuracy, it resulted in slower inference speed and lower FPS, making it unsuitable for time-sensitive industrial applications. SSD MobileNetV2 offered a better balance between speed and accuracy, ensuring

smooth real-time detection with acceptable precision (Mobilenetv and Chimakurth, 2024).

2.4. Real-Time Model Deployment and Evaluation Setup

The model was then converted to a TensorFlow Lite model and deployed on a Windows operating system laptop PC, connected to a 1080P HD USB web camera. The camera was placed inside the same light box to capture real time video of the onions. The predicted class of the onion is displayed on the computer screen with the Confidence Score and the frame rate of the captured video in real time. This output is also displayed outside of the light box in a 16 x 2 LCD display connected to the same Arduino Uno board which is connected to the WS2811 LED strip. The component connections are shown in Fig. 4.

2.5. Real-Time Model Evaluation Using Confusion Matrix-Based Metrics

Using 60 onions from four categories, the model was evaluated for real time detection of onions. By comparing the actual and predicted classes of the onions, binary matrices were created to obtain True Positive, True Negative, False Positive and False Negative values. From these values, accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score were calculated.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$F1\ Score = \frac{2 \times Precision \times Recall}{Precision+Recall} \quad \dots (4)$$

Where, TP is true positive; TN is true negative; FP is false positive and FN is false negative.

Fig. 2. Circuit diagram of the components connected to Arduino Uno

2.6. Physical System Evaluation

The physical component of the system including the lighting box, Raspberry Pi, camera, and display were successfully deployed and were able to classify onion samples in real time. However, due to the manual placement of onions inside the lighting box, it was not possible to measure the sorting speed or throughput rate (*e.g.* onions sorted per minute). The system provided immediate classification outputs upon detection, indicating low inference latency. To comprehensively evaluate the end-to-end system performance, future development will include a conveyor-based feeding mechanism.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Mean Average Precision (mAP)

The model achieved an overall mean Average Precision (mAP) of 77.94% using the COCO evaluation metric at IoU thresholds ranging from 0.50 to 0.95. This indicates that the model performs well not only in identifying onion categories but also in accurately localizing them within the images. Among the four classes, the highest mAP was recorded for good onions (89.09%), followed by sprouted onions (79.06%), rotten onions (75.24%), and double onions

(68.37%). The relatively lower mAP for double onions may be attributed to their visual similarity with other categories, particularly sprouted onions (Table 1). Overall, the mAP score demonstrates the model's strong capability in both detection and localization, making it suitable for practical use in onion sorting under varied real-world conditions. The accuracy, precision, recall and F1 Score values obtained for the different classes of onions are given in Table 1.

3.2 Accuracy

Accuracy in object detection refers to the proportion of correctly classified objects compared to the total number of objects present in the data set. It is a fundamental metric in evaluating the performance of object detection models, providing insights into how well the model identifies and localizes objects within an image. A high accuracy value signifies that the model is proficient in accurately detecting objects across various classes, while a lower accuracy indicates potential areas for improvement, such as mis-classifications or missed detections. Considering the accuracy values provided for each onion class in Table 2 and the overall accuracy, it's evident that the model performs admirably in object detection tasks.

Table 2. The mean Average Precision (mAP), Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1 – Score for different classes of big onion

Class	mAP, %	Accuracy, %	Precision, %	Recall, %	F1 - Score
Good onion	89.09	88.33	78.57	73.33	0.76
Sprouted onion	79.06	90.00	73.68	93.33	0.82
Rotten onion	75.24	96.49	91.67	91.67	0.92
Double onion	68.37	91.67	91.67	73.33	0.81
Overall	77.94	91.62	83.90	82.925	0.83

With accuracies ranging from 88.33% to 96.49% across different onion categories, the model showcases its capability to accurately identify and classify onions based on their attributes. Particularly noteworthy is the model's exceptional accuracy of 96.49% in detecting "rotten" onions, indicating robust performance in identifying deteriorated produce. Overall, the model achieves a commendable accuracy of 91.62%, signifying its effectiveness in accurately detecting onions across all classes and highlighting its potential for various real-world applications.

3.3 Precision

Precision in object detection refers to the proportion of correctly detected objects among all objects that the model has classified as belonging to a particular class. It provides insights into the model's ability to accurately identify objects of interest without falsely classifying unrelated objects. A high precision value indicates that the model makes fewer false positive classifications, resulting in a more reliable detection of objects within images. Considering the precision values provided for each onion class in the Table 1 and the overall precision, it is apparent that the model demonstrates commendable precision in object detection tasks. With precision values ranging from 73.68% to 91.67% across different onion categories, the model showcases its capability to accurately classify onions based on their attributes.

Notably, both "double" and "rotten" onions exhibit the highest precision values at 91.67%, indicating the model's proficiency in correctly identifying these categories. While "good" onions have a slightly lower precision of 78.57%, "sprouted" onions exhibit the lowest precision at 73.68%. Nonetheless, the overall precision of 83.89% underscores the model's effectiveness in accurately detecting onions across all classes, highlighting its potential for various real-world applications.

3.4 Recall

Recall in object detection refers to the proportion of correctly detected objects of a particular class out of all the objects belonging to that class in the data set. It provides insights into the model's ability to capture and identify all instances of a specific object class, thereby minimizing false negatives. A high recall value indicates that the model can effectively detect most of the objects belonging to a particular class, ensuring comprehensive coverage of the target objects within images. Referring to the values of recall in Table 1 for each onion class, and the overall recall, it is evident that the model demonstrates commendable performance in recalling objects across various categories. With recall values ranging from 73.33% to 93.33%, the model showcases its capability to effectively identify

onions based on their attributes. Notably, “sprouted” onions exhibit the highest recall at 93.33%, followed closely by “rotten” onions with a recall of 91.67%. While both “good” and “double” onions maintain consistent recall values at 73.33%, the overall recall of 82.915% underscores the model’s effectiveness in capturing a significant proportion of onions across all classes, highlighting its robust performance in object detection tasks.

3.5 F1 Score

The F1 score, a metric commonly used in classification tasks, combines precision and recall into a single value, providing a balanced assessment of a model’s performance. A high F1 score indicates both high precision and recall, with values ranging from 0 to 1. It is particularly useful when the class distribution is imbalanced, as it considers false positives and false negatives equally. Referring to the data in Table 1, combining the individual F1 scores provided for each class, the overall performance of the model can be assessed. With a good F1 score of 0.76 for “good” onions, the model exhibits reasonable performance, while scoring slightly higher for “double” onions at 0.81. Moreover, it demonstrates even better performance in identifying “sprouted” onions, achieving an F1 score of 0.82. Impressively, the model excels in identifying “rotten” onions, boasting the highest F1 score of 0.92. The overall F1 score of 0.8275 reflects the model’s balanced precision and recall across all classes, indicating its effectiveness in classification tasks. However, there remains potential for enhancement, particularly in refining the identification of less well-performing classes.

During real-time evaluation, several misclassifications were observed, primarily due to lighting variations, partial occlusion, and visual similarities between certain onion categories like overlapping physical features such as protrusions or stem remnants. Inconsistent illumination inside the light box also contributed to missed detections or low-confidence predictions. These errors suggest

that the model is sensitive to environmental factors and the orientation of the object. Enhancing the lighting setup, using image augmentation during training, and incorporating more diverse training samples could help reduce these issues. Furthermore, future work could integrate multi-angle image capture or depth sensing to improve detection robustness under variable conditions.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In developing an AI-based image processing system for sorting big onions, various performance metrics such as mean Average Precision (mAP), accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score, play pivotal roles in evaluating the effectiveness of the model. The overall mAP of the model for accurately sorting big onion was 77.94%. Across different onion classes, the model exhibits robust performance, with an overall F1-score of 0.83. Additionally, the overall accuracy value, precision value and recall value were 91.62%, 83.90%, and 82.92%, respectively. Overall, these metrics collectively indicate the strong performance of the model in accurately identifying big onions, laying a solid foundation for its practical application in real-world sorting processes. However, continuous refinement and optimization may further enhance its performance, ensuring precise and reliable sorting in diverse operational settings.

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